

AN ANALYSIS OF THE COMPONENTS OF SELF ESTEEM IN INDIVIDUAL, TEAM AND DUAL SPORTS PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the significant differences among Individual, Team and Dual Sport Players on the variable Self Esteem. For the purpose of the present study, two hundred fifty eight (N=258), Male subjects between the age group of 18-25 years volunteered to participate in the study. The subjects were purposively assigned into three groups: Group-A: Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar (N₁=86); Group-B: Panjab University, Chandigarh (N₂=86) and Group-C: Punjabi University, Patiala (N₃=86). To measure the level of Self-Esteem of subjects for the present study, the Self-Esteem Inventory (SEI) developed by Prasad and Thakur (1988) was administered. This scale consists of two parameters namely: Personal Perceived Self-Esteem and Social Perceived Self-Esteem. The differences in the mean of each group for selected variable were tested for the significance of difference by One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). For testing the hypotheses, the level of significance was set at 0.05. To conclude, it is significant to mention in relation to Self-Esteem that results of Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to Social Perceived Self-Esteem and Self- Esteem were found statistically insignificant ($P > .05$) whereas, with regards to Personal Perceived Self Esteem were found statistically significant ($P < .05$).

Keywords: individual sport, team sports and dual sports, personal perceived self-esteem and social perceived self-esteem

1. Introduction

Self-Esteem is an essential characteristic for individuals to be successful in sport and general life. Self-esteem is the confidence an individual has in his/her owns ability and how they value themselves accordingly (Rosenberg, 1965a).

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Self-esteem occurs in all individuals in concurrence with a person's thoughts, actions, feelings and beliefs, and is a vital factor for an individual to achieve personal goals and maintain positive mental health (Maslow, 1987). A number of studies have found there to be a positive relationship between sports participation and self-esteem. Research suggests that sport participation increases self-esteem and enhances general psychological well-being. (Slutzky & Simpkins, 2009, Whitehead & Corbin, 1997).

Sport psychologists, practitioners and other researchers have suggested why self-esteem is enhanced by sports participation. This positive connection between self-esteem and sports participation is likely due to the positive health and social characteristics associated with being involved in sport. Also, the increase in body image and physical competence that comes with being involved in sport are factors closely associated with self-esteem. (Bowker, 2006).

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Selection of Subjects

For the purpose of the present study, Two Hundred Fifty Eight (N=258), Male subjects between the age group of 18-25 years (Mean $\pm$ SD: Age 21.97 ± 2.03 (yrs), Body Height 167.8 ± 5.338 (cm), Body Mass 64.73 ± 3.692 (kg)) volunteered to participate in the study.

The subjects were purposively assigned into three groups:

- Group-A: Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar (N₁=86);
- Group-B: Panjab University, Chandigarh (N₂=86);
- Group-C: Punjabi University, Patiala (N₃=86).

All the subjects were informed about the objective and protocol of the study. The demographics of subjects are brought forth in Table 1.

Table 1: Subject's Demographics (N=258) of Players of Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar (N₁=86), Panjab University, Chandigarh (N₂=86) and Punjabi University, Patiala (N₃=86)

Variable (s)	Sample Size (N=258)			
	Total N=258	Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar (N ₁ =86)	Panjab University, Chandigarh (N ₂ =86)	Punjabi University, Patiala (N ₃ =86)
Age (yrs)	21.97 $\pm$ 2.03	21.71 $\pm$ 2.086	21.83 $\pm$ 2.115	22.36 $\pm$ 1.84
Body Height (cm)	167.8 $\pm$ 5.338	167.2 $\pm$ 5.419	167.3 $\pm$ 5.69	168.8 $\pm$ 4.79
Body Mass (kg)	64.73 $\pm$ 3.692	63.48 $\pm$ 3.668	64.87 $\pm$ 3.579	65.83 $\pm$ 3.482

N; sample size, yrs; years, cm; centimeters, kg; kilograms.

Figure 1: Subject’s Demographics (N=258) of Players of Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar (N₁=86), Panjab University, Chandigarh (N₂=86) and Punjabi University, Patiala (N₃=86)

The details of subject’s (i.e., Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports) of Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar (N₁=86), Panjab University, Chandigarh (N₂=86) and Punjabi University, Patiala (N₃=86) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The details of subjects

Sample Size (N=258)								
Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar (N ₁ =86)								
Individual Sport (N=31)			Team Sports (N=40)			Dual Sports (N=15)		
Athletics (12)	Archery (12)	Gymnastics (07)	Volleyball (12)	Basketball (12)	Hockey (16)	Badminton (5)	Chess (5)	Lawn-Tennis (5)
Panjab University, Chandigarh (N ₂ =86)								
Individual Sport (N=31)			Team Sports (N=40)			Dual Sports (N=15)		
Athletics (12)	Archery (12)	Gymnastics (07)	Volleyball (12)	Basketball (12)	Hockey (16)	Badminton (5)	Chess (5)	Lawn-Tennis (5)
Punjabi University, Patiala (N ₃ =86)								
Individual Sport (N=31)			Team Sports (N=40)			Dual Sports (N=15)		
Athletics (12)	Archery (12)	Gymnastics (07)	Volleyball (12)	Basketball (12)	Hockey (16)	Badminton (5)	Chess (5)	Lawn-Tennis (5)

2.2 Selection of Variables

To measure the level of self-esteem of subjects for the present study, the Self-Esteem Inventory (SEI) developed by Prasad and Thakur (1988) was administered. This scale consists of two parameters namely:

- i. Personal Perceived Self Esteem;
- ii. Social Perceived Self-Esteem.

3. Design of the Study

This is an exploratory study that has employed method of data collection and analysis quantitatively. The purposive sampling technique was used to attain the objectives of the study.

4. Statistical Analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 14.0 was used for all analyses. The differences in the mean of each group for selected variable were tested for the significance of difference by One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). For further analysis Post-Hoc Test (Scheffe's Test) was applied. For testing the hypotheses, the level of significance was set at 0.05.

5. Results

For each of the chosen variable, the result pertaining to Analysis of variance (ANOVA) among Individual, Team and Dual Sports players with regards to variable Self Esteem are presented in the following tables:

Table 3: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to Personal Perceived Self Esteem

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Between Groups	2305.242	2	1152.621	3.035	.050
Within Groups	96829.537	255	379.724		
Total	99134.779	257			

The p-value is .050. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

- It is evident from **Table 3** that results of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to **Personal Perceived Self Esteem** were found statistically significant ($P < .05$). Since the obtained F-value was found significant, therefore, post-hoc test was employed to study the direction and significance of differences between paired means. The results of post-hoc test have been presented in **Table 4**.

Table 4: Analysis of post-hoc test among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to Personal Perceived Self Esteem

Multiple Comparisons			
Group (A)	Group (B)	Mean Difference	Sig.
Individual Sports (82.8172)	Team Sports	2.51720	.646
	Dual Sports	8.70609	.050
Team Sports (80.3000)	Individual Sports	-2.51720	.646
	Dual Sports	6.18889	.194
Dual Sports (74.1111)	Individual Sports	-8.70609	.050
	Team Sports	-6.18889	.194

- A glance at **Table 4** showed that the mean value of Individual Sports group was 82.8172 whereas Team Sports had mean value as 80.3000 and the mean difference between both the groups was found 2.51720. This shows that the Individual Sports group had demonstrated significantly better on Personal Perceived Self Esteem than their counterpart's Team Sports group.
- The mean value of Individual Sports group was 82.8172 whereas Dual Sports had mean value as 74.1111 and the mean difference between both the groups was found 8.70609. This shows that the Individual Sports group had demonstrated significantly better on Personal Perceived Self Esteem than their counterpart's Dual Sports group.
- The mean value of Team Sports group was 80.3000 whereas Dual Sports had mean value as 74.1111 and the mean difference between both the groups was found 6.18889. This shows that the Team Sports group had demonstrated significantly better on Personal Perceived Self Esteem than their counterpart's Dual Sports group.

Table 5: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to Social Perceived Self-Esteem

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Between Groups	976.923	2	488.462		
Within Groups	45599.701	255	178.822	2.732	.067
Total	46576.624	257			

The p-value is .067. The result is not significant at $p > .05$.

Table 6: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to Self Esteem

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Between Groups	1686.094	2	843.047		
Within Groups	102094.437	255	400.370	2.106	.124
Total	103780.531	257			

The p-value is .124. The result is not significant at $p > .05$.

- It is evident from **Table 5** that results of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards **Social Perceived Self-Esteem** were found statistically insignificant ($P > .05$).
- It is evident from **Table 6** that results of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to **Self Esteem** were found statistically insignificant ($P > .05$).

6. Conclusions

To conclude, it is significant to mention in relation to Self-Esteem that results of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to Social Perceived Self-Esteem and Self Esteem were found statistically insignificant ($P > .05$) whereas the results of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) among Individual Sport, Team Sports and Dual Sports players with regards to Personal Perceived Self Esteem were found statistically significant ($P < .05$).

7. Recommendations

Sports psychologists, Sports physician, coaches and athletic trainers may utilize the findings of the present study by preparing or modifying the existing training schedules for Individual, Team and Dual Sport Players.

Since this study had only focused on to find out the significant differences among Individual, Team and Dual Sport Players on the variable Emotional Maturity, Mental Health, Mental Toughness and Self-Esteem, it is recommended that further studies be carried out on much more broadly based (Larger multinational) sample; the better to aid generalization.

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